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Program Studi: Ilmu perpustakaan dan Informasi Islam

Mata Kuliah : Literasi Informasi

Resensi Jurnal

Judul: Information overload: a concept analysis

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Penerbit : Emerald Publishing Limited

Tahun terbit: 1 Januari 2023

Halaman: 144-159

Keywords: Information overload, Concept analysis, Cognitive overload, Computer science, Information science, Information retrieval, Information technology Paper type Research paper

Sinopsis: In their overview, Bawden and Robinson (2021) have shown that IO is an important problem which has propagated to organisations, societies and individuals, and that there is no consensus on the definition. They group the causes of IO in four groups: quantity of information, diversity, complexity and novelty of information, pushed information, and factors related to individuals. In our paper, we offer a model which encapsulates these various causes. The first two groups (quantity of information and intrinsic characteristics of information) fit within our intrinsic and extrinsic information characteristics trigger; pushed information falls within our working environment trigger, and the factors related to the individuals go within the brain ability and cognition trigger. We have studied the various causes and consequences of IO in CS and IS research from the period spanning 2010 to September 2020 with the aim of providing a comprehensive definition for IO. This work provides a reproducible approach to describing, clarifying and defining IO in CS and IS. It also showed that from 2010 to September 2020, the papers discussing CO are actually tackling IO. We categorised the various elements of the concept of IO and provided researchers with a clearly operationalised model to better study, observe and work towards reducing the human problems associated with IO.

Keunggulan: 1. This work provides a reproducible approach to describing, clarifying and defining IO in CS and IS. It also showed that from 2010 to September 2020, the papers discussing CO are actually tackling IO. We categorised the various elements of the concept of IO and provided researchers with a clearly operationalised model to better study, observe and work towards reducing the human problems associated with IO.

2. All people now a days find it easier to get information either from the internet, television or radio

Kekurangan: 1. In our introduction, we presented the most popular definition of IO, which is to consider it a phenomenon that happens when there is a large amount of relevant and potentially useful Information overload: a concept analysis 153 information; however, this information becomes an obstacle rather than a benefit to an individual's learning. We also highlighted the definition of CO from cognitive psychology, in which CO is understood to happen when the amount of information held by the individual is too high and will minimise individuals' cognitive performance. However, we believe these definitions are both limited in the context of the modern age. This work has clearly highlighted that IO is more than just about the quantity of information and its relevance.

2. The writing is difficult to understand because it is all in English, so it must be translated so that you know the contents of this article